

Studies on the Coordination of Pyridine and β -Picoline with *Bis*-(2-hydroxyacetophenone oximato) and *Bis*-(2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone oximato) nickel(II)

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Adducts of bis-(2-hydroxyacetophenone oximato) nickel(II) and bis-(2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone oximato)-nickel(II) with pyridine and β -picoline having general formula NiL_2L_2' have been prepared and they are characterized by their electronic spectral and magnetic properties. The ligand-field and nephelauxetic parameters evaluated from the spectra using ligand-field theory of spin-allowed transitions are found consistent with six-coordinate structure for these adducts.

It is observed that diamagnetic, square-coordinated complexes of Ni(II) develop paramagnetism when they are dissolved in various organic solvents¹. This behaviour of the Ni(II) complexes was attributed to the equilibrium between square and tetrahedral forms of the complexes. It is also well-known that diamagnetic, square-coordinated Ni(II) has a strong tendency to increase its coordination number by interaction with additional ligands at right angles to the plane of the parent molecule. By this way the resulting complex is found to have octahedral structure and paramagnetic behaviour^{2,3}. The present work describes the preparation of such paramagnetic Ni(II) complexes. These NiL_2L_2' complexes have been prepared by mixing the solutions of 4-coordinated Ni(II) complexes of 2-hydroxyacetophenone oxime (HAO) and 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone oxime (MHAO) NiL_2 with pyridine and β -picoline, L' .

Experimental

HAO (M.P. 116°C) and MHAO (M.P. 143°C) were prepared by the aqueous ethanolic alkali method and were recrystallized from ethanol. All chemicals used were of reagent grade. $Ni(HAO)_2$ and $Ni(MHAO)_2$ were prepared using the literature method^{4,5}. The adducts of the above complexes with pyridine and β -picoline were prepared as follows. First, the NiL_2 was dissolved in the base L' and warmed for some time on a water bath. The resulting solution was cooled and then petroleum ether was added to it to precipitate the adduct which was filtered, washed with ether and dried by suction. The solid adducts are found to be unstable, showing a tendency to give up the base and form the original compound. For establishing the composition, metal content in each adduct was determined by independent gravimetric and volumetric methods. As the adducts are unstable, the amount of base was determined by heating the adducts to constant weight in an oven at 80°. The metal contents of the residues

obtained as above correspond to that of the parent complex, NiL_2 , the residue also shows diamagnetic behaviour. These observations establish the identity of the residues with parent compounds.

A "Sartorius" semi-micro Gouy-balance was used to determine the magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes. The Gouy tube was calibrated using $[Hg Co(NCS)_4]^0$. The diffuse reflectance electronic and solution electronic spectral measurements were made on Beckmann DU spectrophotometer. The solutions for spectral measurements were made by dissolving the parent complex in adequate quantity of appropriate base to prevent dissociation of base from the adduct and then diluting with benzene.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) reveal 1:2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry for the parent complexes and 1:2:2 (metal : ligand : base) stoichiometry for the adducts.

The diffuse reflectance and solution electronic spectral data are given in Table 1 and 2 respectively. The magnetic moments of the complexes are included in Table 1. It can be seen that the parent complexes NiL_2 must have a square planar structure, as they exhibit a strong characteristic band around 16,660 cm^{-1} . Diamagnetic behaviour of these complexes also support the planar structure. The solution spectral data for the adducts consistent with an octahedral structure. Thus all the adducts show three bands in their normally expected regions for Ni(II) octahedral complexes. The spectra are quite similar to those of the complexes of the type $NiL_4X_2^0$.

Assuming an average effect from the ligand atoms^{9,10} it is possible to use the energy levels for d^8 configuration in octahedral field. The following three spin allowed transitions are possible.

$$\nu_1 : {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_2 : {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\nu_3 : {}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

According to the weak field approximation the energy of the first band ν_1 , corresponds to $10Dq$. While the second and third transitions are mixed by configuration interaction and their energies can be determined by

$$\nu_{2,3} = \frac{1}{2} (15B + 30Dq) \mp \frac{1}{2} [(15B - 10Dq)^2 + 120Dq]^{1/2} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

The interelectronic repulsion parameter, B , was obtained using the following different equations¹¹.

$$(a) \quad B = \frac{2\nu_1^3 + \nu_2^3 - 3\nu_1\nu_2}{(15\nu_2 - 27\nu_1)} \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$(b) \quad B = \frac{\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1}{15} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$(c) \quad B = \frac{1}{75} [3\nu_1 \pm \{25(\nu_2 - \nu_3)^2 - 16\nu_1^2\}^{1/2}] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

From the following equations we have calculated both B and $10Dq$ using ν_2 and ν_3 .

$$(d) \quad 10Dq = \frac{1}{34} [9(\nu_2 + \nu_3) \pm \{81(\nu_2^2 + \nu_3^2) - 178\nu_2\nu_3\}^{1/2}] \dots (8)$$

$$B = \frac{\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 30Dq}{15} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$$(e) \quad B = \frac{1}{510} [7(\nu_2 + \nu_3) \pm \{49(\nu_2 + \nu_3)^2 + 680(\nu_2 - \nu_3)^2\}^{1/2}] \dots (10)$$

$$10Dq = \frac{1}{3} (\nu_2 + \nu_3) - 5B \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

Because of instrumental limitations of measurements it was not possible to obtain the ν_3 band. However, we do observe strong intense tail in the region 25000 cm^{-1} . This may allow us to conclude that, the spin allowed transition, ν_3 , would exist in the range where our complexes exhibit strong charge transfer absorptions. Therefore, we have used eq. (5) to

calculate then B and using this B and observed $\nu_1 = 10Dq$, we have calculated ν_3 by eq. (4). This calculated ν_3 along with observed ν_1 and ν_2 were used to calculate B_{35} by equations (6) and (7). After getting $10Dq$ and B , equation (4) was used to get ν_2 and ν_3 . The values, thus obtained are given in Table 2. Examination of Tables 1 and 2 suggests the following.

(i) The difference in the chemical nature of the ligands has little effect on the $10Dq$ values. It means, that atoms beyond the first coordination sphere have only a small influence on the absorption spectrum^{10,12}.

(ii) The appearance of ν_1 band in the spectra shows some signs of splitting, suggesting that it is not possible to consider that an average effect from the ligand atoms determines the spectral shape. In fact, in Oh symmetry it is not possible to find any splitting of the ν_1 band. However, in lower symmetry, D_{4h} , ν_1 frequently splits. These are assigned as transitions to the ${}^3B_{2g}$ and 3E_g (components of ${}^3T_{2g}$) levels. Thus the structure in the ν_1 band may be assigned to the lowering of symmetry in the adducts.

(iii) For all the systems, the transition energy, ν_3 , is calculated and this was fitted for other methods. From the table it appears that, the calculated energies are very close to the observed energies. Band fittings by method (e) give rather larger $\delta\nu$ in all the systems studied. Therefore, it may be concluded that this may not be a better method.

(iv) The ratio ν_2/ν_1 of the frequencies of the first and second band maxima lies in the range required for octahedral complexes of nickel (II)¹³.

(v) All the complexes have magnetic moments in the range 3.1 to 3.3 and thus confirm the octahedral coordination around Ni(II). In an attempt to correlate the spectral and magnetic data, μ_{eff} were calculated using $10Dq = \nu_1$ and $\lambda_o = -315$ by

$$(\mu_{eff})_{cal.} = \mu_{eff}^s \left(1 - \frac{4\lambda_o}{10Dq} \right) \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

The calculated values (Table 1) are found to be in good agreement with the observed values, indicating small orbital contribution because of the spin-orbit coupling between the first excited state ${}^3T_{2g}$ and ground state. This also suggests the validity of the ligand field parameter $10Dq$, electron-electron repulsion parameter, B and the observed μ_{eff} .

(vi) ν_1 bands in the diffuse reflectance spectra of the adducts were observed as very broad bands. We also feel that the compounds would have probably decomposed during the measurements, and therefore, it is rather difficult to attach any significance to it.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC DATA

Compound	%Base L' Found (Cal.)	% Nickel Found (Cal.)	Magnetic moment B.M. Found (Cal.)	Solution Spectral bands (Cm^{-1})	Diffuse Reflectance spectral band (Cm^{-1})
1. Ni(II) (HAO) ₂	—	16.6 (16.36)	Diamagnetic	16660	15850
2. Ni(II) (HAO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂	34.95 (34.48)	11.25 (10.93)	3.23 (3.17)	11100, 18180	11750 19610
3. Ni(II) (HAO) ₂ (PY) ₂	28.46 (30)	12.15 (11.78)	3.10 (3.17)	11180, 18180	11750, 19610
4. Ni(II) (MHAO) ₂	—	15.55 (15.23)	Diamagnetic	16660	16130
5. Ni(II) (MHAO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂	32.36 (33)	10.48 (10.26)	3.15 (3.17)	11140, 18180	11750, 19610
6. Ni(II) (MHAO) ₂ (PY) ₂	28.97 (28.43)	11.05 (10.83)	3.17 (3.17)	11100, 18180	—

TABLE 2—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES IN cm^{-1}

Compound	Method	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	$\beta_{2,5}$	$\delta\nu_1$	$\beta_{3,5}$	ν_2/ν_1
Ni(HAO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂	Expt.	11100	18180	—				1.64
	(a)	10 Dq	fitted	30905	1052		0.97	
	(b)	10 Dq	18180	30905	1052	± 0	0.97	
	(c)	10 Dq	18170	30915	1050	± 10	0.97	
	(d)	11140	fitted	fitted	1044	± 40	0.97	
Ni(HAO) ₂ (PY) ₂	(e)	12117	fitted	fitted	849	± 1007	0.79	
	Expt.	11180	18180	—				1.63
	(a)	10 Dq	fitted	30365	1000		0.93	
	(b)	10 Dq	18180	30365	1000	± 0	0.93	
	(c)	10 Dq	18165	30380	998	± 15	0.92	
Ni(MHAO) ₂ (PY) ₂	(d)	11190	fitted	fitted	1005	± 10	0.93	
	(e)	11671	fitted	fitted	902	± 491	0.85	
	Expt.	18100	18180	—				1.64
	(a)	10 Dq	fitted	30905	1052		0.97	
	(b)	10 Dq	18180	30905	1052	± 0	0.97	
Ni(MHAO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂	(c)	10 Dq	18170	30915	1050	± 10	0.97	
	(d)	11140	fitted	fitted	1044	± 40	0.97	
	(e)	12117	fitted	fitted	849	± 1007	0.79	
	Expt.	11140	18180	—				1.63
	(a)	10 Dq	fitted	30560	1020		0.94	
Ni(MHAO) ₂ (β -picoline) ₂	(b)	10 Dq	18160	30560	1020	± 0	0.94	
	(c)	10 Dq	18160	30580	1016	± 20	0.94	
	(d)	11160	fitted	fitted	1024	± 20	0.94	
	(e)	11867	fitted	fitted	902	± 727	0.86	

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